

JAPAN'S LOCAL SELF-GOVERNMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract: The thesis deals with the local self-government system of Japan and its structural structure. It is noted that there are some similarities between the Japanese system and Uzbekistan.

Key words: Japan, self-government, system, civil society, neighborhood

According to the Japanese constitution, self-governing bodies are elected by the population (for 4 years)[1]. Another important aspect of the matter is that village elders, city mayors or prefecture (province) governors have the same status. This prevents the absorption of the most basic rights and freedoms of local self-government bodies by relatively powerful and well-resourced levels of power, and prevents local issues from being sidelined.

There are two levels of local government in Japan, the upper level is the prefecture, and the lower level is the district, city, and village self-governments. The practice of delegation is also widely used in the distribution of powers. The federal government is subordinate, and the prefectures delegate their powers to the lower self-governing bodies. In this case, it is recorded as delegation that the higher authority gives the issues related to its authority to the lower bodies, and this institution is legally strengthened in the Japanese self-government legislation. Delegating in this place is necessary because, while giving broad powers to self-governing bodies, existing powers are temporarily delegated in order to prevent the spread of separatism and the popularization of various opposition parties. This ensures that certain management instruments of the central government are available locally.

Japan has a Ministry of Local Self-Government whose main function is to support citizens' self-government initiatives in the regions. At the same time, one of the unique features of the ministry is that most of the employees working in its central apparatus are specialists who previously worked in self-government bodies. The scope of the exchange of experts includes:

firstly, young employees - they are promoted from the position of specialist in the ministry to the position of head of department in local authorities;

secondly, employees who became heads of relatively large departments and offices in local governments;

and thirdly, officials in the ministerial apparatus who are promoted to prefectures or cities as vice-governors or deputy mayors[2].

The prefectures in the regions are authorized to carry out large-scale works on the construction of roads, airports, railway stations, ports and roads, construction of schools and hospitals, and nature protection.

Subjects on the second level of self-government bodies deal with marriage registration, organization of schools, communal services, maintenance of internal roads and other issues [3].

The uniqueness of the Japanese experience lies in the fact that a nationwide system of self-governing bodies has been formed, the arrival of random persons in both appointed and elected positions has been excluded, and conditions have been created for the career growth of managers and specialists at various levels. At the same time, this growth is carried out horizontally, that is, not to completely different organizations, but vertically throughout the system in which it works. If we pay attention at this point, there are not many specialists who have worked in the system for many years in the process of neighborhood elections and in high-ranking governing bodies . This will not fail to have a certain influence on the formation of specific traditions and values in the system, and on the motivational state of personnel.

The other side of the issue is that the specialists sent to the subsystems serve to keep the powers of the central authority in place. Helps to absorb positive experiences in places. Strengthens ties between regions.

Another interesting aspect of the neighborhood system in Japan is the system of sending pensioners from various corporations to work in the system. This is a system of reserving positions for retirees, known as "hot spot" or "amakudari" in Japan. Commercial corporations take up to 3,000 positions from self-governing bodies for their older employees.[4] Usually, in Uzbekistan, there is a practice of electing or appointing elderly people who have gained experience in other fields and retired to the position of head of the community or relatively high positions in the system. Such situations are one of the elements of Eastern democracy, and for Western experts and the public, this situation is relatively incomprehensible.

This model of decision-making at the local level was described by the Japanese scientist K. Takai as a combination of exogenous and endogenous approaches [5].

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